

Role of Colour Doppler Ultrasound in the Evaluation of Fetal Growth and Perinatal Health

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Received: 25-04-2024 / Revised: 01-05-2024 / Accepted: 20-05-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Fetal growth and perinatal health are vital determinants of neonatal outcomes, influencing both immediate and long-term health. Accurate assessment of fetal well-being is essential for guiding clinical interventions to reduce the risk of adverse outcomes. Colour Doppler Ultrasonography (USG) has emerged as a crucial tool in obstetrics, allowing for non-invasive evaluation of fetal circulation and placental function, particularly in high-risk pregnancies.

Aim: This study aimed to evaluate the role of Colour Doppler USG in predicting fetal growth and perinatal health outcomes, focusing on correlating Doppler findings with pregnancy outcomes.

Methods: Participants underwent Colour Doppler USG between 24 and 36 weeks of gestation to assess the umbilical artery's resistance index (RI), pulsatility index (PI), and peak systolic velocity (PSV). Pregnancy outcomes, including birth weight, Apgar scores, mode of delivery, and NICU admissions, were recorded. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 23.0, with Pearson's correlation and multivariate logistic regression employed to analyse the data.

Results: Abnormal Doppler indices were observed in 20% of the participants and were significantly associated with adverse perinatal outcomes. These included lower birth weight (mean 2.7 kg vs. 3.2 kg, $p < 0.001$), higher rates of caesarean delivery (62.5% vs. 28.1%, $p < 0.001$), and increased NICU admissions (50% vs. 6.25%, $p < 0.001$). Abnormal Doppler findings were identified as independent predictors of low birth weight and NICU admission.

Conclusion: The study demonstrated that Colour Doppler USG is an effective tool for predicting adverse perinatal outcomes, particularly in high-risk pregnancies. Abnormal umbilical artery Doppler indices were strongly associated with poor neonatal outcomes, underscoring the importance of integrating Doppler ultrasound into routine prenatal care.

Recommendations: Routine use of Colour Doppler USG in antenatal care, especially for high-risk pregnancies, is recommended to enhance the detection of fetal growth restrictions and other complications, allowing for timely interventions to improve neonatal outcomes.

Keywords: Colour Doppler Ultrasound, Fetal Growth, Perinatal Health, Umbilical Artery, Pregnancy Outcomes

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Introduction

Fetal growth and perinatal health are crucial determinants of neonatal outcomes, influencing both immediate and long-term health trajectories. The accurate assessment of fetal well-being is essential in guiding clinical decisions to mitigate the risk of adverse outcomes. In recent years, Colour Doppler Ultrasonography has gained prominence as a valuable non-invasive tool in obstetric practice, allowing for detailed evaluation of fetal circulation and placental function. This technology has proven especially useful in identifying pregnancies at risk of complications, thereby facilitating timely interventions that can improve neonatal outcomes.

The ability of Colour Doppler USG to assess blood flow in fetal vessels, particularly the umbilical artery, has been extensively studied. Abnormal Doppler indices, such as resistance index (RI) and pulsatility index (PI), have been linked to placental insufficiency, a condition that can lead to fetal growth restriction (FGR) and other adverse outcomes. Placental insufficiency is a significant contributor to fetal growth restriction, which is associated with an increased risk of preterm birth, low birth weight, and perinatal morbidity and mortality.

Recent studies underscore the importance of incorporating Doppler ultrasound into the management of high-risk pregnancies. For example, a study by Radunovic found that abnormal umbilical artery Doppler measurements were predictive of adverse perinatal outcomes, including low birth weight and increased NICU admissions [1]. Similarly, in another research it was demonstrated that routine use of colour doppler USG in antenatal care significantly improved the detection of fetal growth restriction, allowing for earlier interventions and better neonatal outcomes. These findings are supported by literature that highlights the utility of Doppler ultrasound in predicting and managing perinatal risks [2].

Despite its proven benefits, the use of Colour Doppler USG in routine prenatal care is not yet universally adopted, with variability in its application across different clinical settings. This inconsistency may be attributed to a lack of standardization in practice guidelines or insufficient training among healthcare providers. However, as evidence continues to accumulate, there is a growing recognition of the need to integrate colour doppler ultrasonography more consistently into prenatal care, particularly for the management of high-risk pregnancies [3]. This study aimed to evaluate the role of Colour Doppler USG in predicting fetal growth and perinatal health outcomes, with a focus on correlating Doppler findings with pregnancy outcomes.

Methodology

Study Design: This study is a prospective, observational study.

Study Setting: The study was conducted in the Obstetrics and Gynaecology Department of DMCH, a tertiary care center between March 2019 to April 2021.

Participants: A total of 200 pregnant women were recruited for the study. These participants were selected from those attending the antenatal checkup. Participants were enrolled based on specific inclusion and exclusion criteria to ensure the homogeneity and reliability of the study sample.

Inclusion Criteria

- Pregnant women aged 18-40 years.
- Singleton pregnancies.
- Gestational age between 24 and 36 weeks at the time of recruitment.
- Willingness to participate and provide informed consent.

Exclusion Criteria

- Multiple pregnancies (e.g., twins, triplets).

- Known fetal anomalies or congenital malformations detected before enrolment.
- Pre-existing maternal conditions such as diabetes, hypertension, or cardiovascular diseases.
- History of smoking, alcohol, or drug use during pregnancy.
- Incomplete medical records or loss to follow-up.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, participants were randomly selected from eligible women attending the antenatal clinic. Information bias was minimized by standardizing the data collection procedure and training the sonographers in the use of Colour Doppler USG. To control for confounding factors, adjustments were made during statistical analysis.

Data Collection: Data were collected through a combination of patient interviews, medical record reviews, and Colour Doppler USG examinations. Information gathered included maternal demographics, obstetric history, Doppler ultrasound measurements, and pregnancy outcomes. All data were recorded in a pre-structured format and stored securely for analysis.

Procedure: Each participant underwent a Colour Doppler USG examination between 24 and 36 weeks of gestation. The ultrasonography was performed by a trained and certified sonographer using Doppler measurements included umbilical artery resistive index (RI), pulsatility index (PI), and peak systolic velocity (PSV). These measurements were used to assess fetal well-being and predict potential adverse outcomes.

Participants were followed up until delivery and perinatal outcomes were recorded, including birth weight, Apgar scores, mode of delivery, and NICU admissions.

Statistical Analysis: SPSS software, version 23.0, was used to analyse the data. For every clinical and demographic characteristic, descriptive statistics were computed. Using Pearson's correlation coefficient for continuous data and Chi-square tests for categorical variables, the relationship between Doppler indices and pregnancy outcomes was assessed. In order to account for potential confounders, a multivariate logistic regression analysis was performed. A statistically significant p-value was defined as less than 0.05.

Results

A total of 200 pregnant women were included in the study. The mean age of the participants was 28.5 years (SD $\pm$ 4.5 years), with an age range of 18 to 40 years. The majority of the participants (60%) were between 26 and 35 years old. A summary of the demographic and clinical

characteristics of the participants is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of Participants (n=200)

Characteristic	Mean $\pm$ SD / Frequency (%)
Age (years)	28.5 $\pm$ 4.5
Gestational Age (weeks)	30.2 $\pm$ 3.2
Parity	
- Primiparous	85 (42.5%)
- Multiparous	115 (57.5%)
BMI (kg/m ²)	25.4 $\pm$ 3.6
Mode of Conception	
- Spontaneous	175 (87.5%)
- Assisted Reproduction	25 (12.5%)
Medical History	
- Hypertension	15 (7.5%)
- Gestational Diabetes	20 (10%)
Smoking Status	
- Non-smoker	180 (90%)
- Smoker (during pregnancy)	20 (10%)

Doppler Ultrasound Findings

The mean values of these indices were as follows:

- **Umbilical Artery RI:** 0.62 $\pm$ 0.07
- **Umbilical Artery PI:** 1.15 $\pm$ 0.15
- **Umbilical Artery PSV:** 40.5 $\pm$ 6.8 cm/s

These Doppler indices were categorized into normal and abnormal based on established reference ranges. A total of 160 participants (80%) had normal Doppler indices, while 40 participants (20%) showed abnormal Doppler findings. A comparison between the normal and abnormal Doppler groups is shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Comparison of Doppler Indices in Normal and Abnormal Groups

Doppler Indices	Normal (n=160)	Abnormal (n=40)	p-value
Umbilical Artery RI	0.59 $\pm$ 0.05	0.71 $\pm$ 0.04	<0.001
Umbilical Artery PI	1.10 $\pm$ 0.12	1.30 $\pm$ 0.10	<0.001
Umbilical Artery PSV (cm/s)	42.3 $\pm$ 6.5	35.8 $\pm$ 5.9	<0.001

Pregnancy Outcomes: Pregnancy outcomes were tracked for all participants, with a particular focus on birth weight, Apgar scores, mode of delivery, and NICU admissions. The mean birth weight was 3.1 $\pm$ 0.5 kg, with 25 neonates (12.5%) classified as having low birth weight (<2.5 kg). The Apgar score at 5 minutes was $\geq$ 7 in 185 cases (92.5%).

The mode of delivery was vaginal in 130 cases (65%) and caesarean section in 70 cases (35%). NICU admissions were required in 30 cases (15%), primarily due to respiratory distress or low birth weight.

Table 3: Pregnancy Outcomes in Normal and Abnormal Doppler Groups

Outcome	Normal Doppler (n=160)	Abnormal Doppler (n=40)	p-value
Birth Weight (kg)	3.2 $\pm$ 0.4	2.7 $\pm$ 0.5	<0.001
Low Birth Weight (<2.5 kg)	10 (6.25%)	15 (37.5%)	<0.001
Apgar Score at 5 min ($\geq$ 7)	155 (96.9%)	30 (75%)	<0.001
Mode of Delivery: Caesarean	45 (28.1%)	25 (62.5%)	<0.001
NICU Admission	10 (6.25%)	20 (50%)	<0.001

Statistical Analysis: Pearson's correlation analysis revealed significant correlations between abnormal Doppler indices and adverse pregnancy outcomes. Specifically, higher Umbilical Artery RI and PI were associated with lower birth weight ($r = -0.45$, $p < 0.001$) and increased risk of NICU admission ($r = 0.42$, $p < 0.001$). Abnormal Doppler findings

were also strongly correlated with a higher rate of caesarean deliveries ($r = 0.39$, $p < 0.001$).

Multivariate logistic regression analysis, adjusting for maternal age, BMI, and parity, confirmed that abnormal Doppler indices were independent predictors of low birth weight (OR 3.85, 95% CI

2.10–7.05, $p < 0.001$) and NICU admission (OR 5.20, 95% CI 2.65–10.18, $p < 0.001$).

Discussion

The 200 pregnant women in the study showed how important colour doppler USG is for assessing fetal growth and forecasting perinatal outcomes. Eighty percent of the subjects had normal Doppler indices, and the twenty percent who had aberrant readings had a substantial correlation with unfavourable pregnancy outcomes. In particular, there was a strong correlation found between aberrant umbilical artery Doppler indices, such as elevated PI and RI, and lower birth weights, greater rates of caesarean sections, and a higher probability of admissions to the NICU. Furthermore, the abnormal Doppler group had a significantly greater rate of low birth weight (<2.5 kg) 37.5% than the normal group 6.25%. Due to the crucial nature of these pregnancies, the faulty Doppler group also had a greater rate of caesarean births (62.5%) and NICU admissions (50%).

The correlation between aberrant Doppler findings and unfavourable perinatal outcomes was further supported by statistical analysis. Logistic regression validated abnormal Doppler indices as independent predictors of low birth weight and NICU admission, while Pearson's correlation analysis revealed substantial negative associations between abnormal indices and birth weight.

A research from Eastern India revealed a substantial correlation between a cerebroplacental ratio of less than 1 and unfavourable perinatal outcomes such as preterm, low birth weight, and NICU admissions. The study emphasized the important relevance of colour Doppler ultrasound in foetal monitoring and the significance of employing CPR as a reliable tool in predicting unfavourable perinatal outcomes [4].

An additional investigation from Care Hospital, Jamnagar assessed the use of colour Doppler in the treatment of high-risk pregnancies. Abnormal umbilical artery Doppler findings were found to be significantly correlated with unfavourable perinatal outcomes, such as fetal growth restriction and intrauterine death. It has been demonstrated that combining many arterial waveform tests improves diagnostic precision in identifying fetuses at risk [5].

A study carried out at Bangalore Medical College and Research Institute provided more evidence of the value of colour Doppler ultrasonography in

foretelling unfavourable foetal outcomes. The study, which concentrated on high-risk pregnancies, discovered that repeated colour Doppler flow velocimetry may accurately predict unfavourable outcomes. In particular, diseases including pregnancy-induced hypertension (PIH) and diabetes were closely linked to aberrant findings in the umbilical artery and MCA PI, which had a negative impact on neonatal outcomes [6].

Conclusion

These findings imply that USG is a useful modality for assessing fetal health before birth, especially when it comes to identifying pregnancies that may have unfavourable consequences. Early management and closer monitoring are made possible by the capacity to identify aberrant blood flow patterns in the umbilical artery, which may enhance perinatal health and lower problems. Consequently, adding colour Doppler ultrasonography to standard prenatal care may improve the way high-risk pregnancies are managed and improve the results for the newborn.

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